

THE HEALTH COOPERATIVES AS REPOSE TO HEALTHCARE CHALLENGES AND COVID19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract: Health cooperatives are not developed in Serbia, but during 2020 there was created Initiative for reopening health cooperatives submitted to the Parliament explaining benefits of such organisational form and requesting change of public policies based on the previous research. This paper propose model that might be of practical power for the existing settings of healthcare system of Serbia, particularly reaching vulnerable groups in rural areas. Global experiences of healthcare cooperatives are presented especially considering COVID19 pandemic. Methodology is based on the analysis of the literature and synthesis of historical and modern aspects of health cooperatives in order to propose model of worker based health cooperatives that should be created into the rural areas in order to achieve results more effective than current in provision of the healthcare services.

Keywords: health cooperatives, rural areas, Republic of Serbia, cooperative model, COVID19

INTRODUCTION AND HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF HEALTH COOPERATIVES IN SERBIA

Health cooperatives in Republic of Serbia have a significant and long history. One of the first ever mentions of Health cooperatives in Serbia was identified during the First Congress of Agricultural Cooperatives (1895), when was opened discussion about *health funds* within agricultural cooperatives. Interestingly, same model of organization of cooperatives was

later established in Japan (and newer form is known as Koseiren cooperatives) (1). First health cooperatives have been created in 19th century in Serbia and one of such early examples was health cooperative opened in today city of Lazarevac (2, 13;43); (3, 52;53). At the time of 19th century, health cooperative movement was not stable and widespread but the idea about development of such organisational form already existed (e.g. rural areas of then Kingdom of Serbia). At the beginning of 20th century, there was very difficult period for entire country due to the two Balkan wars (1912-1913) and the First World War (1914-1918). This extremely difficult period resulted in post-war crises and major issues were connected with following: lack of institutions, demographic concerns, different epidemiological issues, poverty etc. (4,225). Following creation of *Kingdom of Serbs, Croats and Slovenes (1918-1929)*, idea of development of health cooperatives raised again and after WWI first health cooperatives have been developed in 1921. Following that period, until the 1941 – health cooperatives have been multiplying and reaching number of 100 with similar number of created health stations (2,42).

During the WWII, health cooperatives stopped their work and there have been noticed numerous issues with invaders (i.e. health cooperatives were burned, medical stuff were killed etc.) (5,25-63); (2,42). After the WWII, health cooperatives have been re-established, but only until 1949 when those organizations have been included to healthcare system of then Yugoslavia. Following that period, until recently (2020), there have not been any interest in health cooperatives although these type of organizations have been included in Law on Cooperatives (Official Gazette of Republic of Serbia, no.112/2015) (6). In 2020, there was created Initiative for opening health cooperatives which was submitted to the Parliament of Republic of Serbia with request for public hearing (6). Additionally, National Plan for rural revitalization (*Ser. Nacionalni Program za preporod sela Srbije, in further text National plan*) created by Board for villages of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts and Ministry for regional development – includes concept of health cooperatives (for the first time after decades) (7). In following text we are extracting paragraph from the mentioned National Plan explaining views on the role of the health cooperatives in rural areas (8):

“In the public promotion of the new Serbian cooperative, it is necessary to point out the need to establish health cooperatives, which would also cover rural areas. Such cooperatives would take care not only of the treatment of the sick in the villages but of the various types of their preventive action raising the general level of health culture, which is very low among the peasants.”

Those activities are a good signal showing that changing of public policies might happened in the future and health cooperatives might become more frequent organization type in healthcare system in Serbia. In order to facilitate change of public policies and implementation of health cooperatives it is important to present the prospective organizational models that might be competitive solution in resolving ongoing healthcare issues in Serbia (9); (10); (11); (12); (13); (14). In this paper, we are mostly interested in rural areas of Republic of Serbia having in mind health equity, health equality and quality of medical services. Therefore, in further text we are going to propose model of health cooperatives that might efficiently resolve some of the issues of healthcare system, affecting also selected problems of medical professionals including employment and emigration. Also, we are showing examples of health cooperatives from world with special attention to the cases of cooperatives during COVID19 pandemic.

BRIEF PRESENTATION OF THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM CHALLENGES CONSIDERING HEALTH COOPERATIVES MODEL APPROACH IN RURAL AREAS

Inequality in access to healthcare system is visible in rural areas comparing to the population in cities. This is particularly oriented to the agricultural workers and vulnerable groups (e.g. unemployed women and children). Access to healthcare institutions is not the same for the rural and urban population. In addition, access to primary and secondary healthcare is not the same leading us to the question about health equality in those regions?

Having this said, there is no standardization in the rights to access healthcare for the rural and urban areas and this is exactly the problem where state should consider wider implementation of health cooperatives.

Another major problem is related to agricultural workers and their health insurance access. Namely, according to different sources, their current debt to the Republic Fund for Health Insurance of Republic of Serbia is measured in billions of Serbian dinars. There have been requested changes of law on the health insurance in Republic of Serbia in order to allow calculation of the fees for health insurance based on the profit instead of current setting which is requiring fees based on the size of the farm and potential for production, sales and profit.

Basis of insurance	Total number of insured persons	Insurance holders	Members
Employed	2.889.675	1.774.849	1.114.826
Unemployed	46.323	35.372	10.951
Pension users	1.962.002	1.751.378	210.624
Entrepreneurs	304.503	181.475	123.028
Agriculture workers	204.628	104.709	99.919
Insured on the basis of state budget	1.326.651	924.532	402.119
Other	167.7	133.922	33.778
Total	6.901.482	4.906.237	1.995.245

Table 1, Health insurance structure in Republic of Serbia (15)

Another example of inequality is connected with rights of the vulnerable groups in rural areas : maternity allowances are not the same in value for the rural and urban citizens and primary healthcare is not approachable as in the cities. Health culture and edification, health risks, mental health, healthy food production and environmental concerns of the rural areas population also requires more attention and Government of Republic of Serbia noticed those concerns (8).

WHAT ARE THE ACTUAL TRENDS IN GLOBAL DEVELOPMENT OF HEALTH COOPERATIVES AND WHAT ARE THE ADVANTAGES OF SUCH ORGANISATIONS?

Health cooperatives are developed in numerous countries globally. According to data obtained from International Health Cooperative Organization IHCO (sector of International Cooperative Alliance - ICA), health cooperatives are on the rise in many countries. This arising trend is not only within scope of number of newly opened health cooperatives, but also it is connected to creation of more complex organizations with more and more employees, members and number of services provided.

Countr y	Yea r	Number of organizatio ns	Turnov er (million)	Currenc y	Empley es	Users (millio n)	Users (% of the populatio n)
Australi a	2014 - 2016	175	9,244	AUD	15.659	3.6	14.9
Belgium	2016	785	1,002	EUR	19.702	13.2	116.3
Brazil	2015	1,933	-	-	96.023	24	11.6
Canada	2013	130	63	CAD	1.132	0.4	1.1
Colomb ia	2013 - 2015	152	9,87259 4	COP	17.383	8.6	17.7
France	2014	1,832	-	-	36.344	12.3	18.4
Italy	2014	6,756	9,235	EUR	233.397	5.5	9.1

Japan	2014-2015	145	1,359,320	JPY	91.969	12.2	9.6
Singapore	2015	4	114	SGD	2.271	1.7	30.3
Spain	2016	507	14,499	EUR	52.006	6.4	13.8
Sweden	2015	298	149,411	SEK	19.367	13.6	137.3

Table 2. Status of health cooperatives in observed countries (16)

*missing data on health insurance cooperatives sector

Having in mind requirements for opening health cooperatives, Initiative for reopening health cooperatives in Republic of Serbia (in further text: Initiative) has recognized following relevant aspects (7):

“Health cooperative models, like other types of cooperatives, are prone to self regulation, and problems in unregulated markets have detrimental and significant consequences that we could see in the global financial crisis of 2007–2008 when financial instruments were secured by “toxic assets” and world markets collapsed. As a counterpart to such a form of business, cooperatives that are complex with self-regulation operate in a very transparent and responsible manner, and in order for self-regulation to be successful, it must include honesty, concern for others, and social responsibility. Therefore, cooperatives should include a high ethical component in their work, and it is also important to prevent the formation of false cooperatives by law. In order to understand the importance and the way cooperatives work, it is of great importance to include adequate programs in the academic and professional education that train new experts in cooperatives. The development and future of cooperative businesses should be continually encouraged through scientific research, which is the responsibility of the competent alliances or scientific and research institutions with

which cooperatives should have a high degree of cooperation. Also, international support should be there in order to develop the health cooperative movement further.”

When considering rural development and health cooperatives, it is important to mention that numerous countries have been assigning roles to health cooperatives exactly in order to resolve healthcare issues within its rural areas. We have such examples in both historical and modern concepts. Namely, in Kingdom of Serbia (later Kingdom of SHS; Kingdom of Yugoslavia and Yugoslavia (FNRY) - prospectively), health cooperatives had significant impact on rural areas. At time after the WWI, health cooperatives have been implemented in rural areas in UK, USA, India, Poland, France, Romania, China and many other countries considering them to be effective to resolve that time healthcare issues. When it comes to modern aspects, health cooperatives are operating in Sweden, China, India, Brazil, Argentina and many other countries in rural areas (16).

Why are health cooperatives considered relevant for resolving rural areas healthcare issues? This might depend on the type of organisation, services or products provided etc. However, we can discuss about it *an general* as of the socio-economic predispositions that health cooperatives have. Namely, those organizations are created on the local level (with a strong local inclusion), targeting particular healthcare issues that are not covered by public or private sector due to different reasons (or they have competitive advantage over the other two organisational forms). The important aspect is price of services and development of organization that might be competitive comparing to private organizations and therefore affordable for the users. Structure of the cooperatives includes democracy in decision making, autonomy and usually reinvestment in the business of large portion of the profit. This is also why state is usually considering support of cooperatives in form of subsidies, tax reliefs and other beneficial packages as health cooperatives are creating different socio-economic values through work comparing to investor-based business.

INTERNATIONAL CASES OF HEALTH COOPERATIVES AND COVID19 PANDEMIC

Health cooperatives operate in a large number of countries (Table 2) and within this section we will give an overview of the work of individual health cooperatives in the world in the context of opposing the COVID19 pandemic. Such examples point to the fact of the importance of health cooperatives in the world, and especially in rural areas, and therefore relate to the issue of potential establishment of this organizational form in the Republic of Serbia. Experiences from abroad in the moments when the health system is the most vulnerable, health cooperatives have shown a high degree of autonomy in work, flexibility and innovation as well as fast ways to react.

We can also refer to solidarity as one of the basic principles of cooperatives, which is more needed than before during the COVID19 pandemic, and which has been presented by health cooperatives around the world. On the example of the health cooperative from Italy called "GULLIVER" from Modena, one can see the advantage over other organizational models in the health system of Italy. Namely, this cooperative, which has close to 2000 employees and provides about 530 types of services (17), significantly influenced the change of the supply chain, thus providing all the necessary equipment for its users and cooperative members. The supply chain has changed thanks to a high degree of autonomy and the formation of special teams that have obtained information and equipment on the market through various approaches (including local authorities, consulting with politicians and public decision makers, finding new resources on the market, etc.).

Also, the services were provided outside the standard framework and were implemented soon after the first outbreak of the COVID19 pandemic in Italy (let's not forget that the first European pandemic appeared in Italy when there was not enough information about the virus, measures, etc.).

With an innovative approach, this cooperative has created e-applications that are used to provide psychological support to patients and especially to the users of their numerous gerontology centers. Also, a very small number of people infected with COVID19 is stated, which is due to the timely response as well as the good organization of the institution in order to provide services to its customers in times of great challenges.(17)

Colombian health cooperatives were also up to the task during the COVID19 pandemic. COOMEVA is a health cooperative worth about half a billion US dollars and according to them, solidarity as a cooperative principle is something that is constant in their business both during a pandemic and when there is no pandemic. This health cooperative has successfully redefined its five-year business plan and, by applying cooperative principles, provides adequate health care to a large number of users.

In addition to Italian and Colombian health cooperatives, Indian health cooperatives performed well during the COVID19 pandemic. Namely, the Indian Federation of Health Cooperatives SEWA, thanks to good communication with its users, managed to get their opinion before official state and private health institutions and to make a quality analysis of the needs of its many users during the new situation with the COVID19 pandemic. This federation of health cooperatives was founded in Ahmedabas and employs more than 1.5 million women. (18)

Having in mind these and other successful examples of health cooperatives, the potential of these organizational forms is shown, as well as their significance for the society both during crisis and regular activities.

PROPOSED MODEL OF HEALTH COOPERATIVES FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN SERBIA

Ministry of Health of Republic of Serbia should target particular area of interest considering their deficit in performance. In this paper we are interested in rural areas where healthcare coverage is insufficient due to different reasons. Another step would be that Ministry of Health

(in cooperation with academic and professional institutions and other connected Ministries departments) acknowledge type of issues that are concerning particular rural area and to propose types of health cooperatives that might be effective to resolve such issues (or to adequately minimize them). For example, we could have one rural region with 30 small villages, geographically dispersed within the area, where public health system do not have significant resources (e.g. sufficient number of doctors and medical stuff, number of units for primary care, number of units of secondary care – or large distance for approaching primary/secondary care etc.). Based on such analysis, there should be runned economical analysis that includes size of the investment for the state to cover such issues through health sector or to check the other options: attracting investor-based healthcare facility or health cooperative.

As we are assuming that state would resolve such issues if there was possibility already, we are considering another 2 scenarios: opening private healthcare facility or health cooperative. Having in mind that private healthcare facility is investor-based model, organized in order to be profitable and having in mind average wage in rural areas in Serbia (significantly lower than the average), we are coming to one of the main reasons why private healthcare institutions already do not operate in observed rural areas. Simply, because villagers do not have sufficient incomes to pay out-of-pocket expenses to privately owned clinics despite the fact they need medical services.

Another aspect is related to the prices of medical services. Namely, in Republic of Serbia there is a large disparity of the prices in public and private sector (e.g. cost of CT Scan etc.). In some cases, investor-based model prices are 10 times higher than public health system prices. This also shows instability of healthcare market. Considering that there is no economic interest for investor-based organizations in rural areas and it is too expensive for state to develop strong public healthcare system in rural areas we are proposing model of health cooperatives (as third option) that might be of interest for the patients, state and cooperative entrepreneurs.

This model should be based on the *workers cooperative* that should be created by the medical and other professionals interested in supporting rural areas, but also interested in creating financially self-sufficient organization that should support requirements of the local population creating additional socio-economic values and being profitable at the same time.

If we consider additional aspects that are connected to the unemployed medical stuff in Serbia and level of emigration of medical personal to developed European countries – perhaps health cooperatives might provide solution to previously mentioned challenges through opening another business possibility for those medical workers who would lave country or stay unemployed.

Graph 1, Model of health cooperative and communication with the state on targeting and resolving rural healthcare challenges

Source: Author’s graph

Within graph 1, there is presented model of cooperation between state and workers health cooperative (considering both “entities” have the same goal in targeting rural areas healthcare issues and its resolution). Competitive advantage of health cooperative might be easier to set up comparing to the public institutions in organizational sense. From the other hand allocation of prices for services should be determined in such way to assure profitability (e.g. the prices of the medical services significantly vary from public to private institutions). Therefore, state should have another role in providing subsidies for the health cooperatives in the terms of subsidizing difference in price between market price and price set up by the public healthcare system for the insurers (*Private healthcare medical services prices (P1) - Public health insurance prices (P2) -/+ competitive price regulation (CP)*).

CONCLUSION

This paper presents model approach to resolution of the certain healthcare challenges in rural areas of Serbia. More precisely, this paper provides insights into potential that should be considered by the Public policies creators, government and entrepreneurs in area of cooperatives, in order to allocate appropriate model of health cooperatives that might be interesting for the rural areas.

In this paper, we have especially emphasized the section that shows the work of health cooperatives in the world, their number and complexity with additional reference to the cases of health cooperatives during the COVID19 pandemic. Flexibility, innovation, solidarity and autonomy are just some of the advantages of health cooperatives presented in this paper on the examples of the COVID19 pandemic. Finding and protecting the interests of cooperatives members and users of health cooperatives services in accordance with the basic definitions of the work of cooperatives, is exactly what has proven to be important and effective in the conditions of the newly emerging health crisis.

In addition, health cooperatives follow one of the basic principles of cooperatives - solidarity, in their regular operations and not only in cases of crisis. Therefore, the comment of the representatives of the Colombian health cooperative COOMEVA that members and users of their services do not have to wait for the crisis to see the advantage of solidarity in the work of health cooperatives is certainly good recommendation.

Having in mind challenges of healthcare system of Republic of Serbia in rural areas (demography, primary and secondary care reach out, health edification and education, access to health insurance etc.), we are considering that health cooperative model have the advantages comparing to the public health and investor-based models. Those advantages are mainly seen into the unavailability of those two systems to respond to the challenges for a decades, into the socio-economic benefits of cooperatives, lower expenses for the state (comparing to size of investment for developing adequate public health system), employment of unemployed medical stuff, local recognition and support to local community, organizational architecture of the health cooperatives allowing re-investing of large portions of revenues etc. We should also mention there are many other forms of the health cooperatives, but this model of worker based cooperative was proposed having in mind specificities and requirements of the rural areas in Republic of Serbia. Some of the other forms (based on type of services provided) of coopeatives are also the cooperatives in the area of food protection, safe food production, educational and training cooperatives related to health topics, protection of the environment etc.

Please note that further, more detailed analysis should be performed in order to understand all of the capacities of the proposed model and its implications in practice. However, we are strongly recommending health cooperatives as one capable organizational model that might be used with or without state support creating additional values to the society.

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